

Complex Compounds of Nickel and Copper with *p*-Anisidylbiguanide

S. P. Ghosh and A. K. Banerjee

Complex compounds of nickel and copper with *p*-anisidylbiguanide have been prepared. Halides and sulphates of the complex base and also the complex hydroxide have been described. Nickel complexes have been obtained in two varieties differing in colour, decomposition temperature, and solution spectra. This phenomenon is attributed to *cis-trans* isomerism in square planar structure of the nickel complex; Cu-complex does not show such isomerism.

Phenylbiguanide complexes of nickel and copper were obtained in different modifications by Rây and Chakravarty¹. These differed in colour, solubility, melting point, and rate of hydrolysis. Such differences were attributed to *cis-trans* isomerism because of the planar structure of the complexes with unsymmetrical phenylbiguanide. Several other substituted biguanide complexes of nickel and copper have also been studied²⁻⁹. In these cases also, nickel complexes were obtained with different colour modifications, but copper complexes failed to show such modifications, though the so-called 'size factors' were more favourable. In the present work, complexes of nickel and copper with *p*-anisidylbiguanide have been studied to ascertain the effect of further weighting the biguanide molecule.

Nickel-*p*-anisidylbiguanidinium hydroxide and some of its salts, viz., chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate, and nitrate, have been obtained in two varieties, yellow (cream) and red. These differ in hydration, decomposition temperature, and absorption in solution. All the complexes are diamagnetic. These lost their hydrated water quickly below 110° without any change in the composition of the complex. The anhydrous complexes regained their hydrated water on exposure to atmosphere. The red forms were found to be more stable as the yellow forms changed to red, when warmed in presence of moisture.

The decomposition temperatures of the two varieties differed by about 10°; in the case of the complex nitrate, it was 20°.

In the visible region, the two varieties show maximum absorption in different regions, the difference being about 25 m μ . The same behaviour has also been observed by us for

1. This *Journal*, 1941, 18, 609.
2. Rây and Ray, *ibid.*, 1944, 21, 163.
3. Rây and Dutt, *ibid.*, 1948, 25, 563.
4. Rây and Siddhanta, *ibid.*, 1943, 20, 250.
5. Ray, *Science & Culture*, 1954, 20, 35.
6. Rây and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 155.
7. Ghosh and Chatterjee, *ibid.*, 1955, 32, 222; 1953, 30, 369.
8. Ghosh and Banerjee, *ibid.*, 1955, 32, 32.
9. Banerjee and Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1961, 38, 237.

the different varieties of nickel-*p*-phenethylbiguanide complexes. In the case of nickel-2-guanidinium benzimidazole complexes, the absorption maxima show a difference of about 10 m μ .

From these evidences it can be suggested that the two differently coloured varieties of nickel complexes represent *cis-trans* isomerism (I), the complex having a square planar, inner level *dsp*² structure.

where X = Cl, Br, I, NO₃, or $\frac{1}{2}$ SO₄. The copper complexes of substituted biguanides fail to show such isomerism.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Anisidylbiguanide hydrochloride was prepared by refluxing a mixture of *p*-anisidine hydrochloride and dicyandiamide in equimolecular proportion for 4½ hr. The solution was cooled when impure crystals of the hydrochloride separated. These were purified by recrystallisation from hot water after treatment with bone charcoal; m.p. 212°. (Found: C, 43.86; H, 5.61. C₉H₁₃ON₅·HCl requires C, 44.35; H, 5.77%).

Nickel Complexes

α-Nickel-p-anisidylbiguanidinium Hydroxide.—To a mixture of a solution of nickel sulphate (1*M*) and *p*-anisidylbiguanide hydrochloride (2*M*) a slight excess of a dilute solution of NaOH was added dropwise with constant stirring. A reddish buff-coloured precipitate separating (slowly) was quickly filtered, washed with cold water, and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid caustic soda. The dried sample is orange in colour and is insoluble in water and ethanol. It liberates ammonia from ammonium salts. {Found: Ni, 11.16; N, 26.71. [Ni (C₉H₁₃ON₅)₂] (OH)₂ requires Ni, 11.23; N, 26.78%}.

α-Nickel-p-anisidylbiguanidinium chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate, and nitrate were obtained on triturating the complex base with the corresponding ammonium salts at the room temperature (25°). When evolution of ammonia had ceased, the crystals were filtered, washed with cold water, and dried in air. The complex salts are sparingly soluble in cold as well as in hot water. The colour and analyses of the complex salts are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Complex salts.	Colour.	*Formula.	% Nickel.		% Anion.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Chloride	Yellowish white	X.Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	10.50	10.41	12.42	12.50
Bromide	Pale cream	X.Br ₂ .H ₂ O	9.04	8.99	24.50	24.51
Iodide	Cream	X.I ₂ .H ₂ O	7.90	7.86	33.89	34.02
Sulphate	Light brick-red	X.SO ₄	10.40	10.28	17.01	16.82

β-Nickel-*p*-anisidylbiguanidinium chloride, bromide, iodide, and sulphate were obtained when the complex base was digested on the steam bath with the corresponding ammonium salts. When the evolution of ammonia had stopped, the crystals were filtered, washed with cold water, and dried in the atmosphere. Colour and analyses of the complex salts are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Complex salts.	Colour.	Formula.	% Nickel.		% Anion.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Chloride	Dirty yellow	X.Cl ₂ .0.5H ₂ O	10.53	10.56	12.63	12.79
Bromide	Orange-yellow	X.Br ₂	9.23	9.24	24.81	25.20
Iodide	Cream	X.I ₂ .0.5H ₂ O	8.02	7.96	34.40	34.43
Sulphate	Brick-red	X.SO ₄	9.96	10.28	10.71	16.82

All the α - and β -salts are diamagnetic. The colour of the β -salts are deeper in shade than the corresponding α -salts.

Copper Complexes

Copper-*p*-anisidylbiguanidinium hydroxide was precipitated when to solutions of copper sulphate (1*M*) and *p*-anisidylbiguanidinium chloride (2*M*) a dilute solution of ammonium hydroxide was added dropwise. The light violet precipitate was filtered and washed with cold water. It was purified by dissolving in HCl (dil.) and reprecipitating with dilute ammonia. The precipitate was filtered, washed with cold water, and dried in CO₂-free air. {Found: Cu, 11.53; N, 25.50. [Cu(C₉H₁₃ON₅)₂](OH)₂. 2H₂O requires Cu, 11.60; N, 25.57%}. The base is moderately soluble in hot water. It liberates ammonia from ammonium salts.

The chloride, bromide, iodide, and sulphate of the complex base were obtained when the moist base was added slowly to the hot solution of the corresponding ammonium salts. The complex base dissolved in the hot ammonium salt solutions, forming a pale pink colour, which on cooling deposited the corresponding salts. The precipitates were filtered, washed with cold water, and dried in air. The salts are paramagnetic. Colour and analyses of the complex salts are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Complex salts.	Colour.	*Formula.	% C o p p e r.		% A n i o n.		Absorption.
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	
Chloride	Light pink	X.Cl ₂ .1.5H ₂ O	11.07	11.04	12.30	12.34	570,650m μ
Bromide	Violet-pink	X.Br ₂ .H ₂ O	0.77	0.60	24.32	24.41	560,630
Iodide	Brownish cream	X.I ₂ .2H ₂ O	8.31	8.27	33.00	33.09	
Sulphate	Violet	X.SO ₄ .H ₂ O	10.80	10.74	16.19	16.23	565,645

Absorptions of these copper complexes in water show two peaks in regions 560-570 m μ and 630-650 m μ . According to Ráy and Ray¹⁰, the absorption peak at 650-660 m μ is typical of monobiguanide, whereas at 520-530 m μ it is characteristic of bis-biguanide chelates. In aqueous solution thus, like other biguanide complexes, some monobiguanide complexes are also formed. Thermal decomposition temperatures were determined in a "Stanton" thermobalance with a heating range of 4°/min. Table IV shows the results of thermal decomposition of nickel-*p*-anisidylbiguanidinium complexes.

TABLE IV

Nisalts.	Yellow/cream.	Red.
Chloride	240°	250°
Bromide	230°	235°
Nitrate	220°	240°
Sulphate	160°	170°

Absorption in aqueous solution was studied with a Hilger spectrophotometer, using 10 mm cells. The results are recorded in Table V.

TABLE V

Ni-biguanidinium salts.	Yellow/cream.	Red.	Ni-2-guanidinium benzimidazole.	Yellow/cream.	Red.
<i>p</i> -Anisidyl-chloride	590 m μ	615 m μ	Chloride	605 m μ	610 m μ
iodide	580	605	Bromide	600	515
sulphate	585	610	Iodide	580	600
<i>p</i> -Phenetyl-chloride	587	612	Nitrate	600	610
sulphate	585	610	Sulphate	590	610

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